

Animal wound healing properties of some plants - an overview

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Abstract

Research on wound healing drugs is a developing area in modern biomedical sciences. Scientists who are trying to develop newer drugs from natural resources are looking toward the Ayurveda, the Indian traditional system of medicine. Several drugs of plant, mineral, and animal origin are known for their wound healing properties and most being derived from plant origin. Some of these plants have been screened scientifically for the evaluation of their wound healing activity in different pharmacological models and patients, but the potential of most remains unexplored. In a few cases, active chemical constituents were identified. Some plants, namely, *Hydnocarpus wightiana*, *Azardica indica*, *Lantana camara*, *St. John's Wort*, *Aloe vera*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Chromolaena odorata*, *Helianthus annuus*, *Jasminum auriculatum*, *Ginkgo biloba*, *Cedrus deodara*, *Curcuma longa*, *Centella asiatica* were experimentally found to be effective and possessing medicinal properties for curing wounds in animals. This article presents a limited review of plants used in wound healing in animals.

Introduction

Work-related, malicious, infectious, or accidental skin damage in animals is frequently associated with substantial pain, malfunctioning, limited production, disability, bleeding, or even death in animals. Wounds may be classified as open (with disruption of skin or mucous membrane continuity) or closed (no disruption of the continuity though underlying tissues will be damaged, e.g., bruises or hematomas). Most wounds, particularly open wounds, are home to a diverse bacterial, fungal, and viral flora. Although most bacterial diseases may be treated with conventional antibiotics, there have been some reports of bacteria that are multi-drug resistant (Nolff *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, there is need for alternative therapies in wound management.

Due to their efficacy, accessibility, expanding scientific evidence on them, and commercial interests, natural goods such as herbal treatments have helped human and animal populations in wound management for ages. Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antipruritic, hypotensive, proliferative, hypoglycemic, and analgesic phytoconstituents are found in most plants

or parts of plants, and are frequently used in wound management and healing (Barreto *et al.*, 2014). However, the usage of herbal medications is raising safety concerns, as only around 10% of them are properly characterized and/or made according to strict quality standards (Ifeoma and Oluwakanyinsola, 2013). Because plants contain a wide range of phytochemicals that can be hazardous to key organs and other living tissues, assessing the possible toxic effects of plants and their products is critical to ensure safety (Jothy *et al.*, 2011). Throughout history, several herbal preparations have been employed in the management and treatment of wounds. A few plants/plant products with this promise are discussed:

Hydnocarpus wightiana

The oil of *Hydnocarpus* spp. has been used as anti-leprosy drug and as an antiparasitic drug in the treatment of guinea worm infestation. The oil of *Hydnocarpus* given orally or administered topically helps to heal the wounds and gangrene faster in leprosy and diabetic patients. The wound healing effect of oil of *Hydnocarpus* spp. significantly increases the strength of scar tissues and collagen tissue and hydroxyl-proline content in the wounds. *Hydnocarpus* oil administered orally promoted epithelization, but not wound contraction (Oomen *et al.*, 2000). External application of oil of *Hydnocarpus* spp. and its paste shortens the epithelization period. Oil may act as adjuvant in healing of wounds and ulcer in leprosy patients and therefore, may be clinically useful.

Azardica indica

It is commonly called as Neem and the plant has diverse medicinal properties. Neem oil contains margosic acid, glycerides of fatty acids, butyric acid and trace of valeric acid. Various active principles are nimbidin, nimbidal, azardirachtin, nimbin, azadirine, gedunin, salanin. They have diverse medicinal activities. Neem oil is especially beneficial for curing skin ailments. Oil is used for dressing for foul ulcers, eczema and skin diseases like ringworm, scabies and mange in dogs. It is a powerful insect repellent, antibacterial, anti-fungal, anti-viral, anti-inflammatory and also strengthens the body's overall immune responses. Neem oil contains fatty acids which build collagen, promote wound healing and maintain the skin's elasticity. The active ingredients of neem oil help in the process of wound healing and the skin is able to retain its suppleness as the wounds heal. Neem oil has a high content of essential fatty acids. They keep the site moist and give a soft texture to the skin during the healing process. Alcoholic extract of neem is useful in eczema, ringworm and scabies. Neem leaf extracts and oil from seeds has proven anti-microbial effect. This keeps any wound or lesion free from secondary infections by microorganisms.

Lantana camara

Lantana camara has abortifacient, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory and wound healing

properties. The hydroalcoholic extract and fresh juice of leaves favor wound contraction (Kurian, 1995). The plant is potentially toxic and its toxicities include nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, photosensitization, dermatitis, intestinal haemorrhage; therefore, the use of this plant needs to be carefully regulated.

St. John's Wort (Hypericum spp.)

St. John's wort has an age-old history of safe and effective usage in many folk and herbal remedies. It is claimed to be useful in mental depression, anxiety, sleep disorders, menstrual cramping, sciatica and arthritis. The blossoms have been used in folk medicine to relieve patients suffering from ulcers, gastritis, diarrhea and nausea. This plant has an antiseptic action, relieves inflammation and promotes healing when used externally on cut surfaces of the body. The oral tincture of *Hypericum* has a remarkable effect in lacerated and suppurated wounds with restoration of tissue vitality. Pro-healing action of *Hypericum* tincture is evidenced by enhanced epithelization phase with an increase in wound contraction rate and granulation tissue breaking strengths (Rao *et al.*, 1991).

Aloe vera

Aloe is also known as "lily of the desert" or the plant of immortality. Egyptians recorded use of this herbal plant in treating burns, infections and parasites as early as 1500 B.C. Its clear gel has a dramatic ability to heal wounds, ulcers and burns by forming a protective coating on the affected areas and speeding up the healing process. Various constituents of *Aloe vera* have been shown to have anti-inflammatory activity. They also stimulate wound healing. Topical *Aloe vera* gel is useful in healing minor burns and the application of the gel is harmless as hypersensitive reactions to it are rare (Schmidt and Greenspoon, 1991).

Tridax procumbens

The juice of the leaves of this plant is used by villagers to arrest bleeding from cuts and bruises in animals. This juice accelerates two phases of healing namely epithelization and collagenization; however it retards scar formation and granulation. The whole plant extract of *Tridax procumbens* has the greatest pro-healing activity; however, the leaf extracts of this plant also promote wound healing. The plant increases the lysyl oxidase, protein and nucleic acid content in the granulation tissue (Udupa *et al.*, 1998).

Chromolaena odorata

The aqueous extract and the decoction from leaves of *Chromolaena odorata* have been used throughout for the treatment of soft tissue wounds and burn wounds. It enhances hemostatic activity and stimulates granulation tissue and re epithelization processes (Lee, 1995). The extract also

inhibits wound contraction reversibly. Therefore, the plant can be of much therapeutic value in minimizing post burn scar contracture and deformities.

***Helianthus annus* Linn.**

In traditional medicine the plant is used by tribals for inflammation of eyes, sores, dysuria, colic, tiger bites and bone fractures (Jain and Tarafdar, 1970). The whole plant alcoholic extract of *H. annus* if applied in the form of an ointment on the wound leads to a significant reduction in total healing period.

Jasminum auriculatum

Juice of leaves of *J. auriculatum* is beneficial in wound healing. When applied in the form of jelly locally on wounds, promotes wound healing. Fresh juice of the leaves increases the tensile strength in the linear wounds by improving collagenation in the early phase of healing. Ghee medicated with *J. auriculatum*, on topical application accelerates the healing time of second degree burn wounds up to six days by enhancing the mucopolysaccharide accumulation (Deshpande and Upadyaya, 1967).

Ginkgo biloba

Ginkgo biloba (*Salisburia aduatifolia*) is also known as maiden hair tree. It exhibits a variety of interesting pharmacological activities such as increase in blood fluidity, antioxidant, membrane stabilizing, improvement in cognition and pro-healing. Its preparations promote epithelization without altering wound contraction. *Ginkgo biloba* also increases granulation tissue breaking strength and the content of hydroxylproline without altering granulation tissue mass weight. Pro-healing action of the *Ginkgo biloba* is due to the presence of flavonoids (Bairy and Rao, 2001).

Cedrus deodara

Its oil has been reported to possess anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial activities. *Cedrus deodara* has also shown wound healing properties and is particularly useful in infective wounds (Dikshit and Dixit, 1982).

***Curcuma longa* Linn.**

Commonly known as turmeric or haldi. *Curcuma longa* possesses antibacterial, anti-fungal and anti-inflammatory activities. The part used are rhizomes and it contains curumin, turmeric oil or turmerol and 1,7-bis, 6- hepta-diene-3, 5-dione. Curcumin has potent anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities. Volatile oil isolated from *C. longa* also exhibits antibacterial and potent anti-inflammatory activity. *Curcuma longa* also contains protein, fats, vitamins (A,B,C), all of which

have an important role in wound healing and regeneration. The anti-inflammatory property and the presence of vitamin A and proteins in turmeric result in the early synthesis of collagen fibers by mimicking fibroblastic activity (Kumar *et al.*, 1993). Juice of the fresh rhizome is commonly applied to recent wounds, bruises and leech bites. A paste of turmeric and leaves of *Justica adhatoda* is rubbed on skin affected with prurigo and eczema. It can also be mixed with ginger oil to prevent skin eruptions.

Centella asiatica

Centella asiatica (Brahmi) also known as “gotu kola”, is the main herb in Ayurveda for nervous system, it is used in the repair of nervous tissue from crushing trauma, such as spinal injury, neuromuscular disorders, and to increase general brain function and memory concentration. It is used extensively in the treatment of leprosy, a host of skin conditions including cellulites, varicose vein and wounds. The active principles of *Centella asiatica* are triterpenes and asiaticoside which are responsible for promotion of rapid wound healing (Shukla *et al.*, 1999). Aqueous extract of *Centella asiatica* promotes wound healing on topical administration wounds by increasing the collagen content and thickness of epithelium. Topical administration of the aqueous extract increased cellular proliferation, promoted the collagen synthesis at the wound site.

Miscellaneous

Plants such as *Cissus quadrangularis*, *Adenium multiflorum* and *Erythrina abyssinica* have many applications in veterinary medicine world over. Traditional applications of *C. quadrangularis* (Vitaceae or grape family) include managing wounds, anthrax, hematuria, elephantiasis, broken and dislocated bones, anemia, dehydration, gout, syphilis and other venereal diseases, gastrointestinal disorders, cardiovascular diseases, scurvy, ear and eye diseases and metabolic disorders (Ruskin *et al.*, 2014; Gulzar *et al.*, 2015). Apart from being useful as an arrow poison in game hunting and fishing *A. multiflorum* has also many ethnoveterinary medicinal uses. The uses include the management of animal wounds, boils, warts, poultry watery/bloody diarrhea, eye and ear diseases, ticks and lice and tooth decay (Shukla, 2015; Marandure, 2016). *Erythrina abyssinica* is one of 11 species in the *Erythrina* genus that have known medicinal applications. It is used for the management of inflammation, microbial and parasitic infections, eyes infections and kidney diseases (Kone *et al.*, 2011).

Conclusion

The effects of the medicinal plants have been observed on tissue regeneration and strength using experimental animal models. No clinical data has been reported with the same rigor using most of these products. This should not detract wound scientists from examining and reappraising

such products that have been mentioned in textbooks of Ayurvedic or traditional medicine. It is likely that these plants were used because they were commonly available. Wound healing is a clinical challenge especially where resources are limited. It therefore behoves the wound fraternity to examine all options available with which wound management may be bettered for the benefit of all.

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